

OVERALL PROGRESS

Genetic evaluation and utilization

CICA 7, a new rice variety

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A new semidwarf rice variety, CICA 7, has been selected by the integrated rice program of the Instituto Colombiano Agropecuario (ICA) and the Centro Internacional de Agricultura Tropical (CIAT), with cooperation of the Federacion Nacional de Arroceros (FNA). It was released to farmers in May 1976.

CICA 7 was selected from the cross IR22/IR930/Colombia 1 made in 1970 at the Palmira Experimental Station. It is high yielding and has extra-long grains and excellent milling and cooking qualities. It is tolerant of blast disease *Pyricularia oryzae* Cav. and resistant to the direct damage of the leafhopper *Sogatodes oryzicola* (Muir).

It matures in 125 to 135 days and is well adapted to irrigated areas between sea level and 1,200 m above sea level.

CICA 9, a high yielding rice variety

Manuel J. Rosero, director until June 1976, and Jorge Vallejo, Edmundo Garcia, Ernesto Andrade, and Carlos Franco, agronomists, ICA Rice Program

A semidwarf rice variety, CICA 9, was released to farmers in May 1976 after it was selected by the integrated rice program of the Instituto Colombiano Agropecuario (ICA) and the Centro Internacional de Agricultura Tropical (CIAT), with cooperation of the Federacion Nacional de Arroceros.

CICA 9 was selected from the cross IR665/IR841/C46-15, made in 1971 at the Palmira Experimental Station. It is long grained, with a high yield-capacity and good milling and cooking qualities. It is tolerant of blast disease (*Pyricularia oryzae* Cav.) and resistant to the direct damage of *Sogatodes oryzicola* (Muir).

It matures in from 126 to 138 days after planting and is well adapted to the lowland rice areas of tropical Latin America.

Collecting rice germ plasm in the Uttar Pradesh hills of India

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The hill district of Uttar Pradesh, India, including Nainital, Almora, Pithoragarh (Kumaon), Chamoli, Uttarkashi, Pauri, Tehri, and Dehradun (Garhwal), presents a range of stresses to rice, from moisture, cold, blast, and brown spot. A program of collection, screening, utilization, and conservation of germ plasm from the area

was initiated in 1973. Of 292 collections made in 1973 from the Almora district, 11 lines resistant to blast have been identified by Rana and others. In 1976, 98 collections were made from Pauri, Tehri, Uttarkashi, Chamoli, and Almora – mainly from direct-seeded, rainfed terraces. The purification, screening, and cataloguing of the collections have begun. Additional tours are planned.

High yielding varieties like IR24, Ratna, Saket 4, and VL 8, which are suitable for the irrigated valleys, are gradually spreading. There is yet no suitable variety for the upland terraces. Local upland and transplanted varieties like Matmari, Inakat, Rikhua, Laldhan, Gyarsu, Chaurhdan, Munjala, and Chima 4 are popular.

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Agronomic characteristics

Evaluation of rice cultivars for their response to limiting nutrients

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At the International Institute of Tropical Agriculture, certain paddies had been used to investigate yield reductions when certain nutrients were limited. Paddies with low levels of different nutrients were planted in 1976 to 25 cultivars (see table) that had been selected earlier for general performance in West Africa. The question was: would the plants respond differently when a certain nutrient or nutrients (nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, sulfur, or zinc, or all of them) were withheld than when normal, complete nutrients were provided. The cultivars were grown as the paddies' eighth crop from which the particular nutrients had been withheld. Cultivars markedly differed in growth and yellowing symptoms in the different minus-one-nutrient paddies. Yield differences also revealed interactions between nutrient deficiency and variety. The two highest yielding varieties (more than 39 g/plant) across all nutrient-deficient paddies were Pelita I-1 and IR578-95-1-3. Five others yielded moderately well (more than 24 g/plant)

when nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, or all three nutrients were low. They were BG 90-2, BPI 76⁹/Dawn, FARO 15, IR2153-338-3, and TOX 161-5-5. The yield depression with nutrients missing was not consistently correlated with yield when soil fertility was high. The preliminary data indicate that varieties for lowland African soil conditions should be screened for performance at low nutrient levels.

The experiment is being repeated to better quantify yield performance.

Cultivars tested in paddies with histories of low status of different nutrients.

4421 from Colombia	IR578-95-1-3 ^b
4440 from Colombia	IR529-430-4
BG 90-2 ^a	IR2035-242-1
Biplab	IR2071-179-304
BPI 76 ⁹ /Dawn ^a	IR2153-338-3 ^a
FARO 15 ^a	
(BG 679/IR8)	IR2153-550-2-6-3
IAC 1391	IR2863-31-3
IET 1444	OS6
IET 2845	Pelita 1-1 ^b
IR269-26-3-3	
(TOS 78)	Pokkali
IR480-5-9-3-3	TOS 4106
IR503-1-91-3-2-1	TOS 4138
	TOX 161-5-5 ^a
	(TKM 6/ IR269-26-3-3)

^aHighest yielding under low N, P, K, and NPK.
^bHighest yielding across all low-nutrient plots.